

Restructuring the Mindset of Girl Child Towards Earthly Gift: Implication for Counselling

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ABSTRACT

Restructuring the mindset of Girls child towards, earthly gift has become a global concern due to the destruction of lives of good child because of earthly gift. Earthly gift are sometimes very dangerous because of the alarming consequences, such as initiation, bareness and other kinds of social evils. These global act has ravaged the society and make the girl child centre of attack. Government of all levels should endeavor to come up with policies that will put fear into evil men and women minds whose occupation are to use girl-child for rituals. Available reports indicates that communities have been socked with using girl-child for rituals because of earthly gift. Many girls child future had been caged because of earthly gift which are well known in the society. The paper examined the adverse effect of using girl-children for evils and low it can be curbed or mitigated. The paper recommended that Counselling Association of Nigeria should collaborate with national orientation agency to embark on awareness campaign programmes to educate girl – childs on the dangers of earthly gift collection.

Keywords: Restructuring, Girl-Child, earthly gift, counselling information.

INTRODUCTION

The girl – child according to Angel (2015), is any female under the age of 18 years. The girl – child can also be regarded as a female who is within the age group of 10 – 13 years and she is supposed to be in the primary or secondary school. With this, any female that is called a girl is looked upon as a young immature woman who is not yet married.

Meaning and concept of earthly gift

Earthly Gift according to Chile (2019) has been described as those gift which one willingly or unwillingly gives out to someone such as bread, wine, car, shoes, cloths or a gift from God for which his child uses on earth for the good of mankind. It is also a gift often expressed as a service (Mercy, 2020).

In this development, restructuring simply means a process where a girl-child mindset are directed towards meaningful actions or things that are beneficial. It is also a call for restoration of right values or action towards a girl – child, which will help to save the girl – child from destruction and deceit towards young boys. The girl – child can be easily deceived with material things. The society has gone viral on this crime been perpetuated by young boys in the society. Many Girl – child are in the grave because of gifts and so many are mad. Therefore, we need to restructure their mindset towards accepting gift to assist them overcome most of the earthly temptations attached to gifts from people.

Okusa, (2011) opined that earthly Gift is good but any one accepting it, should be careful and prayerful. Some people uses gift to charm or was a girl – child to accept friending them. Earthly gift maketh way for some nonentity or disgruntled elements in the society. They uses gift to entice or deceive some of the girl – child in the society.

Indeed, a woman to engage in gift collection is good but, some human beings are devil incarnate that has subjected so many girl – child to depression, psychological abortion and made them been rejected by their parents. They uses earthly gift to capture some of the girl-child and through the influence of those natural gift, they will agree to sleep with the man. Some of the earthly gifts are evil in the society and it can be avoided through effective restructuring of the girl – child mindset. (Opanda, 2020).

Therefore, it is worthy to mention, that there are ways in which some girl – child get involved in deceit or been enticed through material things or earthly gifts. These includes;

1. **Accepting calling or stopping:** Some girl – child stop from where they are going because a boy demand for their stop to enable the girl – child hear from him. So, in the process of hearing from the boy, he will apply all lies from the pit of hell in order to make the girl – child accept their offer or request. They deceive them through presentation of gifts such as money for recharge cards, data and cloths. They buy shawama and costly shoes and bra to them. Some of the boys are deadly and they apply certain charms or incantation to win a girl-child mind (Abak, 2021).
2. **Gluttony:** When a girl child is glutominis, she can easily fall prey of gift temptations. Any girl under the scourge of gluttonous spirits must be prone to deceive or been a victim of gift temptation. To be gluttonous is very bad and every girl – child mindset need total restructuring to avert the looming danger that has put the spirit of gluttony in them. towards gift offer from men.
3. **Lack of Parental training:** Every girl – child requires proper training. When a girl – child is properly trained, she can escape gift temptations from good for nothing boys in the society. Every girl – child should be properly restructured and be guided on how to avoid accepting gifts from boys.

The role of guidance and counseling in enhancing, the Girl Child regarding earthly gift.

- Guidance and counseling will assist the girl child have sense of belonging and educate her on the possible way's of averting the temptation.
- Counselling of girl child on the adverse effects of gift receiving, will help girl – child avoid certain gifts from certain persons.
- Guidance and counseling will go a long way in putting fear in the minds of girl child from receiving gift.
- Guidance and counseling will assist curb myraids of girl child victims based on gift receiving.

Importance Of Gift Are As Follows

1. To confirm or establish our connection with others. This means that they are a reflection of both the giver of gift to someone we care and allows us to communicate our feeling
2. Gift is important part of our social life and they help build relationships. It is a way of showing gratitude and affection to others.
3. Giving gifts is a surprisingly complex and important part of human interaction, helping to define relationships and strengthen bonds with family and friends.

4. Gift are given to express love, gratitude, and appreciation, and to mark important milestones in one's life.
5. Giving gifts in a relationship is important because it allows you to express your partner and show them how much you care.

Kinds Of Gift

Uzoma, (2021) listed some kinds of Gift: They are as follows:

What is earthly gift?

Earthly gift can be defined as a gift from God for which his child uses on earth for the good of mankind.

This gift is often express as a service.

Kinds of earthly gift:

1. Sentimental Gifts: This is item with personal significance, like photo albums or handmade crafts. practical gifts: useful items, such as kitchen gadgets or ties. Experiential gifts: Experiences rather than physical items, like concert tickets or charitable gifts: Donations made in someone's name to a charity.

Kinds of gift we receive from God:

Samson, (2020) stated the following

- God gave man leadership gift
- God released administrative gift to man
- God also give us mercy gift
- God equally released faith gift to us
- God also give us healing gift
- God also give us the gift of miracle
- God equally give us gift of apostleship
- God gave us gift of pastoring
- God gave us gift of teaching
- God gave us gift of evangelism
- God gave us gift of exhortation or encouragement
- God gave us gift of prophecy
- God gave us gift of giving
- God gave us gift of speaking in tongues
- God gave us gift of interpretation and wisdom.

Okendu, (2021) opined that leadership gift are the type of gift that brings up the potentials in a man or woman in terms of leading. To lead is not easy and it involves a lot of commitment and resilience. Leadership is not by mouth and it require the grace of God to lead well.

Administrative Gift: This type of Gift involves a man or woman with sound administrative acumen. To administer others is not easy and you must possess the gift before you can administer effectively.

Mercy Gift: This is the type of gift that is not rampant and it comes from God. The gift of mercy comes from God alone and if you have, the gift, you should praise God and should not abuse it.

Faith: This is another sensitive gift from God, many people do not have it. Faith is a gift from God and should be handled with care. Faith is the only key to live long on earth life without faith is like soup without salt.

Healing Gift: This is the type of gift that is not rampant. Many person are saddled with the responsibility of healing. It is a special gift to those that believe in God and the gift of God reigns forever. Healing gift normally resides with prophets and pastors. It is a calling that emanates from God who is the supreme of the universe.

Miracles: This Gift of miracle is domicile to individuals and prophets. Miracle comes from the supreme of the universe. Miracle is God divine blessings to his children. Miracles are rewards from God to his children.

Apostleship: This is a certificate award given to individuals with special calling by God. One can assume or take up such position only when you are ripe for that position and you can answer it based on confirmation from the church the person worships.

Pastoring Gift: This is a gift from God to those that met the requirement of becoming the pastor. God is the only person that chooses who becomes a pastor.

Teaching Gift: This is a gift that comes from God. Teaching is meant for experience persons and it is for professionals. Teaching gift is a respected field that involves wisdom able and experience peoples.

Evangelism Gift: This is the type of gift that involves men and women of God. It is a calling for professionals in the church. Evangelism calling helps in building children of God who are determined to promote or spread the gospel of God.

Alikor (2023) opined that the gift of exhortation and encouragement helps to building the world of God in clarity with its vision. To encourage men and woman who are determined to showcase the work of God.

Abanel (2024) opined that the gift of prophecy is a gift saddled with prophets of God and pastors. Prophecy is a gift that comes from God and you must be holy or doing the will of God. Prophecy is a revelation from God to save his children from various calamities or evil indictment.

Gift of Giving: Giving gift is a special gift with people that has the heart of God. The bible says; a giver never lacks and it is a confirmation from heaven and its practical manifestation is not hidden. So, we should learn how to give and receive reward from God.

Gift of speaking in tongues: Speaking in tongues is from God. The people saddled with the responsibility of speaking in tongues are pastors, and prophets. The holy spirits communicate with some of them while some of them are his from the pit of hell.

Gift of Interpretation and wisdom: This is the type of gift that hinges on calling and the person must have the fear of God and must be honest and inculcate the right sense of discipline.

Counseling implication:

Earthly gifts are tools or instruments of destructions of lives and instruments of happiness or joy. The activities of some persons in the society is uncalled for and should be resisted. Some people are callous and inhumane and ready to destroy some people by gift giving. The society is in a mess of this ugly development and should be curtailed or curbed. Government should equip counseling associations of Nigeria to provide counseling services that will bring solution to this menace through the following interventions.

Enlightenment campaign intervention:

There is urgent need for counseling association of Nigeria (CASSON) to collaborate with national orientation Agency (NOA) and carry out enlightenment campaign on the need for effective gift collection.

Behaviour modification intervention:

Government at all levels should make deliberate effort to assist counseling association of Nigeria to establish counseling units in all the local government areas in Nigeria that will cater for the problems coming from non-school settings, the primary focus of those units will be to reform maladaptive behaviours of youths in those localities more especially the girl child. These steps and make and you turn.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Government should revisit policies on girl child education and help to eradicate illiteracy and make girl child have sense of reasoning.

Government should make counselling association of Nigeria a viable institution to help eradicate girl child interest on gift receiving and properly educate them on the consequences attached to it. Government should make policies that will help girl child leave a good life and become more reasonable and conscious of avoiding men and women with gift with intention to use them for rituals and other ill – businesses.

CONCLUSION

This paper has thoroughly examined the core causes; life background, consequences and counselling implication of earthly gift receiving by girl child in Nigeria. It is therefore important that the recommendation may be implemented immediately by all concerned authorities.

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